

WORD INITIAL <s> AND <h>
(DAS ANLAUTGESETZ)

This paper addresses why Notker's Anlautgesetz is only marked in the stops and labial fricatives. The essay falls into five parts:

- 1) A brief introduction to Notker and his Anlautgesetz.
- 2) The standard theory--the Anlautgesetz is a syllable initial fortition.
- 3) The standard theory--the process is not marked in the dental or velar fricatives because there are not enough graphs.
- 4) The standard theory--Gothic devoicing and Middle High German fortition are marked defectively where they do not merge phonemes.
- 5) The same logic applied to the Anlautgesetz.

1) Introduction

Notker Teutonicus lived from 950 to 1022, much of his life in the Swiss monastery of Saint Gall. He translated several Latin manuscripts into his native Alemannic, a dialect of Old High German. His works are famous for an alternation in obstruents that has fascinated scholars since Grimm.¹

Initial <b,d,g,u> are written <p,t,k,f>, unless preceded by a sonorant (<l,m,n,r> or any vowel). Articles written in

¹ J. Grimm, *Deutsche Grammatik*, (Göttingen: Dieterich, 1822), p. 107.

German and English both refer to the pattern as Notker's Anlautgesetz, a term perhaps best translated as "law of initials".² Examples are taken from Sehart and Starck.³ The symbols under discussion are underlined.⁴

<u>After Sonorant</u>	<u>Not After Sonorant</u>
	<p>
[ge <u>b</u> reχən]	[durχ <u>p</u> ræχe]
<ge <u>b</u> réchen>	<dúr <u>h</u> práche>
'break, inf'	'break, 3rd sg past subj'
<d>	<t>
[vran <u>d</u> ie hənt]	[vram mért <u>t</u> ie hənt ten]
<frá <u>m</u> díehent>	<frá <u>m</u> mert <u>t</u> íehenten>
'thrive, 3rd pl pres'	'thrive, dat pl pres part'

² H. Penzl, "Notker's 'Anlautgesetz' and Generative Phonology", K. Klar, *American and Indoeuropean Studies. Papers in Honor of M.S. Beeler*, (The Hague: Mouton, 1980), p. 443.

³ E.H. Sehart and W.H. Legner, *Notkers Wortschatz: Das gesamte Material zusammengetragen von E.H. Sehart und T. Starck* (Halle: Niemayer, 1955).

⁴ The prefixes change the meaning of the words, but are not glossed to make it easier to compare the root morphemes. Since syllable boundaries are so crucial to the Anlautgesetz, they are provisionally placed as in Modern German. See W. Benware, *Phonetics and Phonology of Modern German*, (Washington D.C.: Georgetown Press, 1986), pp. 85-86. When the syllable boundary would land on a consonant, it is not marked. Values for vowels are approximate, with long vowels and diphthongs ending in offglides to either [j], [w] or [ə].

<g>	<k>
[gə gaet]	[uwf kaen]
<gegât>	<ûfkân>
'walk, 3rd sg pres'	'walk, inf'
<u>	<f>
[er varen]	[uwf farẽn do]
<eruáren>	<ûffárendo>
'go, inf'	'go, uninfl pres part'

2) Syllable Initial Fortition

This overview of Anlautgesetz scholarship attempts to establish Notker's alternation as a syllable initial fortition.⁵

2.1) Phonological Process

The Anlautgesetz follows a pattern, allowing scholars to posit a process rather than free variation.⁶ Its conditioning is phonological (ex: "unless preceded by a sonorant"). Correspondingly, articles assume that the

⁵ A more impartial overview is offered by N.E. Collinge, *The Laws of IndoEuropean*, (Philadelphia: Benjamins, 1985), pp. 121-125.

⁶ W. Moulton, "Notker's 'Anlautgesetz'", *Linguistic Method Essays in Honor of Herbert Penzl* (The Hague: Mouton, 1979) p. 242; H. Penzl, "Zur Erklärung von Notkers Anlautgesetz", *Zeitschrift für deutsches Altertum*, 86 (1955) p. 204.

process is phonological.⁷

2.2) Fortition After Obstruent or Pause

Most scholars see some type of fortition after obstruent and/or pause.⁸ Clausing posits the opposite (a lenition after sonorant). But he wrestles with a dental stop that does not lenite after sonorant, but remains written <t>:

"Notker's law affected only the *d* which stemmed from Germanic *þ*; the *t* derived from Germanic *d*, on the other hand, showed no alternation."⁹

After Sonorant

<t>

[ver|trij|bet]

<uertrîbet>

Not After Sonorant

<t>

[uws|trij|be]

<ûztrîbe>

⁷ Moulton (1979), p. 242; Penzl (1955), p. 204. For a graphological explanation, see E. Steinmeyer, "Zur Ahd. Literaturgeschichte" *Zeitschrift für deutsches Altertum*, 16 (1873), pp. 138-139. For an extension of the alternation in Notker's strong verbs, see W.P. Lehmann, "Grammatischer Wechsel and Current Phonological Discussion", Maria Tsiapara, *Generative Studies in Historical Linguistics*, (Edmonton: Ling. Res. Inc., 1971) p. 25; W.P. Lehmann, "Observations on Trubetzkoy's Contributions to Phonological Studies", *Romance Philology*, 29 (1975), p. 47.

⁸ W. Braune and H. Eggers, *Althochdeutsche Grammatik* 14. Auflage, (Tübingen: Niemayer, 1987), §§103.

⁹ S. Clausing, "Notker's Anlautgesetz", *Journal of English and Germanic Philology*, 78 (1979), p. 362.

**<uerdrîbet>

'drive, 3rd sg pres'

'drive, 3rd sg past subj'

Clausing proposes that "a slight difference in pronunciation"¹⁰ prevents this /t/ from undergoing Anlautgesetz. But this "one difficulty"¹¹ multiplies by four once syllable boundaries are placed. Syllable initially, all four sets of obstruents contrast after sonorants.¹²

Lenis

/ʃb/

[wɪj|bən]

<uuîben>

'woman, dat pl'

/ʃd/

[wer|dən]

<uuérden>

'become, inf'

/ʃg/

[ʒiŋ|gən]

Fortis

/ʃp/

[ʃkae|pae|re]

<skâpâre>

'sheepskin, dat sg'

/ʃt/

[wor|to]

<uuórto>

'word, gen pl'

/ʃk/

[tsiŋ|kən]

¹⁰ Clausing (1979), p. 363.

¹¹ Clausing (1979), p. 372.

¹² Moulton (1979), pp. 245-246.

<ś <u>ín</u> gen>	<ć <u>ín</u> ken>
'sing, inf'	'prong, dat sg'
/śv/	/śf/
[w <u>o</u> l <u>v</u> a]	[h <u>e</u> l <u>f</u> en]
<uu <u>ó</u> l <u>u</u> a>	<h <u>é</u> l <u>f</u> en>
'wolf, nom pl'	'help, inf'

2.3) Full Fortition After Obstruent or Pause

Clausing writes:

"There are, unfortunately, no Alemannic dialects showing alternation at the beginning of sentences or after pause."¹³

This comes from Penzl,¹⁴ who notes however that a Bavarian dialect¹⁵ does have the process after pause. Lenis phonemes in Swiss only alternate after obstruent, or "bei Emphase und starker Betonung".¹⁶ They do not even merge with fortis, but become merely half fortis.¹⁷ If the Anlautgesetz is to

¹³ Clausing (1979), p. 364.

¹⁴ Penzl (1955), p. 206.

¹⁵ J. Schatz, *Die Mundart von Imst*, (Strassburg: Karl Trübner, 1897), ff26.

¹⁶ Penzl (1955), p. 203.

¹⁷ Penzl's model is A. Heusler's analysis of Baselstadt, Switzerland.

See A. Heusler, "Der alemannische Consonantismus in der Mundart von

have any connection with Modern Alemannic,¹⁸ it must reflect this half fortition. Notker marks something more refined than just phonemes and their mergers; a great rarity in writing systems:

"Bei Schreibungen ist das eine große Seltenheit, wenn systematisch bloß allophonische Verschiedenheiten graphisch ausgedrückt werden."¹⁹

Baselstadt" (1888), reprinted in *Schriften zum Alemannischen*, (Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 1970), p. 31.

¹⁸ Clausing objects to this logic. Forcing the Anlautgesetz to pattern after Modern Swiss presupposes "the continuity of dialects over a thousand-year period", Clausing (1979), p. 365. Perhaps more importantly, it assumes that Notker's texts and these dialect studies reflect the same speech style. Most people cannot even type at a conversational pace, much less transcribe their words onto parchment. But a speech marked "bei Emphase und starker Betonung" might be nearer that of a monk sounding out words as he wrote them down.

¹⁹ H. Penzl, "Die Phoneme in Notkers alemannischem Dialekt", F.M. Raven, *Germanic Studies in Honor of Edward Henry Sehart*, (Coral Gables, Florida: Miami Press, 1968), p. 147. See also H. Penzl, *Lautsystem und Lautwandel in den althochdeutschen Dialekten*, (Munich: Max Hueber Verlag, 1971) p. 104; Penzl (1955) p. 206; Moulton (1979) pp. 242-243. Penzl proposes that Notker was bilingual in Latin and Alemannic, Penzl (1955), pp. 207-208. Since Notker uses voice to distinguish phonemes in Latin, he can recognize a half fortition in Alemannic; even though this distinction does not differentiate phonemes in Alemannic. Penzl's theory may be accepted by the Braune Grammar, see Penzl (1980) p. 444; Braune (1987) §§103 Anm. 2. Valentin agrees with it, P. Valentin, "Althochdeutsche Phonemsysteme (Isidor, Tatian, Otfrid, Notker)", *Zeitschrift für Mundartforschung*, 29 (1962) pp. 347-348. Yet the theory

Yet tape recordings of Zurich Swiss later done by Moulton do show a merger of lenis with fortis after pause.²⁰ A sort of "Inlautgesetz" makes obstruents fortis in clusters.²¹ Moulton even sees evidence for an "Auslautgesetz", with lenis merging with fortis before a pause.²² The Anlautgesetz would not be "one of those rare cases where a writing system symbolizes allophones",²³ but one of three full fortitions in Notker. Penzl in turn later references Moulton to allow for a merger of lenis with fortis after pause.²⁴

2.4) Full Fortition Syllable Initially

Although one can hear pauses on a tape recording, they are only meaningful in a text when transferred to an identifiable boundary. "After pause" becomes "im Anlaut", that is "initially". As Clausen writes:

"Fortunately, we can be fairly sure where the pauses

is rejected by Clausen (1979), pp. 366-367; Collinge (1985), p. 123; Lehmann (1971), p. 20; and Moulton (1979), p. 243.

²⁰ Moulton (1979), p. 250.

²¹ Moulton (1979), p. 246.

²² Moulton (1979), p. 245.

²³ Moulton (1979), p. 242.

²⁴ H. Penzl, "Zur Methodik der historischen Phonologie: Schreibungslautung und die Erforschung des Althochdeutschen", *Beiträge zur Geschichte der deutschen Sprache und Literatur*, 34 (1982), p. 185.

occur, because they are indicated in the manuscript by an orthographic system." ²⁵

He places pauses sentence and clause initially, at high and low punctuation marks. Others have conditioned the alternation at the beginning of words, morphemes or syllables. But as a phonological process, the Anlautgesetz might be cleaner if conditioned by the base phonological boundary, the syllable.²⁶ A preceding sonorant can inhibit the fortition. Increasing grades of boundary (i.e. syllable plus word, syllable plus low punctuation mark, syllable plus

²⁵ Clausing (1979), p. 364.

²⁶ This idea is by no means new. Already in the 19th century, Wilkens argues for a "Silbenanlautgesetz". See F. Wilkens, *Zum hochalemannischen Consonantismus der althochdeutschen Zeit*, (Leipzig: Fock, 1891), §§45. The Anlautgesetz is not the only process that gets cleaner once syllable boundaries are posited. Penzl notes that when "im Inlaut", Germanic */h/ in Notker conditions two contradictory processes: "Notkers verschiedene Entwicklung in *rúhôn* und *rûoh* stimmt mit der bekannten ausgeprägten allophonischen Variation von germ. *h* im Inlaut gegenüber dem Auslaut überein. Aber eine phonetische Erklärung der Kürzung durch Einwirkung des Lenisreibelautes *h* ist ebenso schwierig wie die der scheinbaren Monophthongierung in *zíhen* (aus *zíehen*?), die wie eine genaue Umkehrung des Wandels *ī* zu *ie* in *líeh̄ti*, *níeht*, *íeht* erscheint." Penzl (1968), p. 139. Although Germanic */h/ in /tsiə|hən/ <*zíhen*> is "im Inlaut", a syllable boundary separates it from the preceding long vowel. In /lijh|tij/ <*líeh̄ti*>, /nijht/ <*níeht*>, and /ijht/ <*íeht*>, the /h/ is still "im Inlaut", yet no syllable boundary comes between it and the vowel.

high punctuation mark) can increasingly inhibit the effect of the sonorant. Conditioning the process after obstruent plus syllable boundary then becomes superfluous. Any "Inlaut-" or "Auslautgesetz" can be reformulated as syllable internal or syllable final fortition.

3) Only Marked in /b,d,g,v/

An honest question is why only four of the six sets of obstruents mark Anlautgesetz. The lenis dental and velar fricatives²⁷ do not alternate, regardless if preceded by a sonorant or not.

After Sonorant

<S>

[vyrə|ẓ̌en|dət]

<fúreséndet>

'send, 3rd sg pres'

Not After Sonorant

<S>

[uws|ṣ̌en|do]

<ûzszéndo>

**<ûzzéndo>

'send, 1st sg pres'

²⁷ In order to include /h/ into the same natural class as fricatives, the terms obstruent, fricative, and velar should technically be replaced with nonsonorant, continuant and back. [ṣ̌] marks a fortis /ẓ̌/, and for lack of a better symbol [ḥ] allows for a fortis /h/. Whether the laryngeal undergoes Anlautgesetz depends on how one writes the rule, defines the phoneme. The important issue here will be that fortition alone is not enough to merge /ẓ̌/ with /s/, or /h/ with /χ/.

<h>	<h>
[b _e h _e f t _e t]	[_e nt h _e f ten]
<be <u>h</u> éftet>	<in <u>th</u> éften>
	**<int <u>ch</u> éften>
'fasten, 3rd sg pres'	'fasten, inf'

Kranzmayer places the Anlautgesetz in Old Bavarian. Borrowings from that language into the Slovenian of southern Austria show a fortition in the dental fricatives.²⁸ Collinge notes that "sibilants were not varied".²⁹ But neither analysis comments on why the process is marked defectively in Notker's fricatives. If anything, scholars concentrate on the stops. These form a natural class, and the process in /v/ is not as consistently marked. For example, the Braune Grammar opens its discussion with:

"Bei Notker wechseln die Wortanlaute *b--p, g--k, d--t*, so daß *p, k, t* steht..."³⁰

The alternation between <u> and <f> is not mentioned until the third footnote.³¹

²⁸ E. Kranzmayer, *Historische Lautgeographie des gesamtbairischen Dialektraumes*, (Wien: Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften, 1956), p. 78.

²⁹ Collinge (1985), p. 121.

³⁰ Braune (1987), §§103

³¹ Braune (1987), §§103 Anm. 3.

3.1) Only /b,d,g,v/ Undergo Fortition

The Anlautgesetz would be an odd phonological rule if it was conditioned by a syllable boundary, and yet only affected /b,d,g,v/. A similar process in Modern German (fortition syllable finally, as opposed to initially) affects all obstruents, not just the stops and labial fricatives. Yet some scholars would restrict Notker's rule to only those obstruents that mark it. For example, Clausing writes that in 613 Irish monks founded St. Gall.³² But their language cannot be the source of the Anlautgesetz, which for Clausing is a lenition. In addition to lenition, Old Irish had nasalization and gemination:

"All consonants, not just *p, b, d* (and *f*), were affected. It seems odd that German would take up only the process of lenition and only for a restricted group of sounds."³³

Hoefer excludes the dental and velar fricatives,³⁴ and would even correct spellings in the labials:

"Die Kritik hat meines Erachtens Recht und Pflicht, die wenigen eingedrungenen *v* mit *f* zu vertauschen und somit endlich wenigstens in einem deutschen Denkmal

³² Clausing (1979), p. 361.

³³ Clausing (1979), p. 362.

³⁴ A. Hoefer, "Das Notkersche Anlautgesetz", *Germania*, 18 (1873), p. 202.

reinen Tisch zu machen."³⁵

3.2) Not Enough Graphs

Penzl offers a different theory. For the stops and labial fricatives, Latin has "zweierlei Lautzeichen für Verschlusslaute und einen Reibelaut"³⁶

Nevertheless, for the dental and velar fricatives:

"Eine Variation bei Reibelauten wie *s š ch* ist bei Notker nicht bezeichnet, was Heusler aus 'graphischen Rücksichten' leicht begreiflich fand, da keinerlei passende Lautzeichen zur Verfügung stehen."³⁷

Heusler himself writes:

"Dass dasselbe [Anlautgesetz] sich auf die Verschlusslaute und (weniger konsequent) den labialen Reibelaut beschränkt, ist aus graphischen Rücksichten leicht begreiflich; stand doch für *s* und für *ch* im Anlaut nur ein Zeichen zur Verfügung."³⁸

Weinberg, Schatz, Wilkens and Lehmann doubt that /h/ underwent Anlautgesetz, but still argue for a shortage of graphs in the dentals:

³⁵ Hoefler (1873), p. 203.

³⁶ Penzl (1955), p. 208.

³⁷ Penzl (1955), p. 208.

³⁸ Heusler (1888), §32.

"es unterliegt wohl keinem Zweifel, daß die Dentalspirans *s*, vielleicht auch *h*, soferne es nicht bloßer Hauchlaut geworden war, demselben Wechsel unterworfen war, wie die Labialspirans. Nur konnte dieser aus Mangel an Zeichen nicht ausgedrückt werden."³⁹

"daß man mit einer allgemeinen Verschärfung rechnen muß, daß z.B. *s* fortis und lenis war in *sie singent, mit sinemo churasange*; hier stand ja kein Fortiszeichen zu Gebote."⁴⁰

"Es stand eben nur das eine Zeichen *s* zur Verfügung."⁴¹

"According to Schatz, the rule also applies to s, though there was no symbol to represent a lenis variant of s. If Schatz is correct, only h among the reflexes for the phonological entities involved in Germanic Grammatischer Wechsel lacks alternation in Notker's rule of initials. As the letter h may indicate, it represented a glottal continuant for

³⁹ I. Weinberg, "Zu Notkers Anlautgesetz", *Sprache und Dichtung*, 5 (1911), p. 20.

⁴⁰ J. Schatz, *Althochdeutsche Grammatik*, (Göttingen: Vandenhoeck und Ruprecht: 1927), §§148.

⁴¹ Wilkens (1891), §§136.

Notker."⁴²

Dental and possibly also velar fricatives undergo Anlautgesetz, but Notker cannot mark it in them. For /ž/ and /h/ he has one fricative graph each, but needs two. Alternatively, one could also argue that even if the scribe has two each, he really needs three, since one is used up word initially as an affricate. Perhaps both ideas should be examined before accepting or rejecting a solution based on a shortage of graphs.

3.2.1) Has One Graph Each, Needs Two

Notker's Latin texts have two symbols each for the stops and labial fricatives: <b≠p>, <d≠t>, <g≠c>, and <u≠f>. <k> and <q> might even provide additional stop graphs, or just allographs in complementary distribution with <c>. For the dental and velar fricatives however, Latin only offers one symbol each: <s> and <h>. Even if all obstruents undergo Anlautgesetz, Notker does not have enough graphs to mark it in the dental and velar fricatives.

This is an attractive theory, yet Notker himself contradicts it. Regardless of what symbols Latin has, the scribe contrasts two dental and velar fricative graphs in <z≠s> and <h≠ch>.

⁴² Lehmann (1971), p. 19.

<u>Lenis</u>	<u>Fortis</u>
/ʒ/	/ʃs/
[muw ʒe]	[hej sɛn]
<mûse>	<héizen>
'mouse, nom pl'	'call, inf'
/ʃh/	/ʃx/
[ruhoɛn]	[buw xɛ]
<rúhôn>	<bûche>
'raw, gen pl masc wk'	'belly, dat sg'

3.2.2) Has Two Graphs Each, Needs Three

Perhaps the argument could be taken another step. [ts] and [kx] are transcribed <zz> and <cch> word medially.

[ts]	[kx]
[ʃkat sa]	[blik xɛ]
<scázza>	<blícche>
'treasure, nom pl'	'glance, dat sg'

But beginning a word with <zz> or <cch> must be too great a deviation from Latin spelling patterns, since Notker replaces them with <z> and <ch>. Even though the monk has two graphs each for the dental and velar fricatives, he really needs three. If <z> and <ch> mark affricates word

initially,⁴³ they are not available to mark the fortition of /ž/ and /h/.

Lenis

[#ž]

[vyrə|žen|det]

<fúreséndet>

'send, 3rd sg pres'

Fortis

[#š]

[uws|šen|do]

<ûzséndo>

**<ûzzéndo>

'send, 1st sg pres'

[#ts]

[tsijt]

<zîť>

**<zzîť>

'time, nom sg'

[#h]

[bə|hef|tet]

[#ħ]

[ənt|ħef|tən]

⁴³ If the base phonological boundary is the syllable, the base graphological boundary might be the word. Words can be listed and separated in a text, syllables cannot. Increasing grades of graphological boundary can be expressed in the same way as increasing grades in phonological boundary (i.e. word plus low punctuation mark, word plus high punctuation mark, word plus chapter break). Apparently the graphological boundary remains, even when the word is prefixed. [ts] in <gezîhen> 'pull, inf' is written with <z> as in <zîhen> 'pull, inf'; not with <zz> (**<gezzîhen>) as in <scázza> 'treasure, nom pl'.

<behéftet>

'fasten, 3rd sg pres'

<inthéften>

**<intchéften>

'fasten, inf'

[#kχ]

[kχopf]

<chópf>

**<cchópf>

'head, acc sg'

This too is an attractive theory, yet here again Notker contradicts it. The scribe faces the same situation in the labials. <pf> denotes [pf] word medially, but is replaced by <f> word initially. Yet he still uses <f> to mark the fortition of /v/.

Lenis

[#v]

[er|vareŋ]

<eruáren>

'go, inf'

Fortis

[#f]

[uwf|faren|do]

<ûffárendo>

**<ûfuárendo>

'go, uninfl pres part'

[#pf]

[pflégen]

<flégen>

**<pflégen>

'tend, inf'

The argument is especially weak for the velars. They may only have a two-way [h≠χ] contrast syllable initially.⁴⁴ <chópf> may only mark [χopf] instead of [kχopf].

4) Other Processes Marked Defectively

The Anlautgesetz is not unique in Germanic Philology. At least two other obstruent processes are also conditioned by a syllable boundary and marked defectively: devoicing in Gothic, and fortition in Middle High German. How scholars account for these could give insight into the Anlautgesetz.

4.1) Gothic Devoicing

The fourth century missionary Wulfila translated the Bible from Greek into his native Gothic. His texts mark a twofold process. Voiced obstruents become fricatives after vowels, so /b,d,z,g/ become [β,ð,z,γ]. All obstruents also devoice in certain environments, including syllable finally.⁴⁵

[β,ð,z,γ] here would become [f,þ,s,χ], and presumably merge the voiced /b,d,z,g/ with their corresponding voiceless fricatives. This twofold process is marked in three out of four sets of obstruents: /b≠f/, /z≠s/, and /d≠þ/. Examples

⁴⁴ Braune (1987), §§144 Anm 2, Anm 5.

⁴⁵ W. Braune and A. Ebbinghaus, *Gotische Grammatik* 19. Auflage, (Tübingen: Niemeyer, 1981), §§79.

are taken from Bennett.⁴⁶

Voiced

/b/

<giban>

'give, inf'

<gaf>

'give, 3rd sg past'

/d/

<stada>

'place, dat sg'

<staþ>

'place, acc sg'

/z/

<ize>

'he, gen pl'

<izs>

'he, nom sg'

Voiceless

/f/

<hiufan>

'mourn, inf'

<hauf>

'mourn, 3rd sg past'

/b/

<qiþan>

'say, inf'

<qaþ>

'say, 3rd sg past'

/s/

<urreisan>

'arise, inf'

<urrais>

'arise, 3rd sg past'

⁴⁶ W. Bennett, *An Introduction to the Gothic Language*, (New York: Modern Language Association, 1980).

Yet in the fourth set /g≠h/, the process is not marked.

Voiced	Voiceless
/g/	/h/
<daga>	<slaha>
'day, dat sg'	'stroke, dat sg'
<dag>	<slah>
**<dah>	
'day, acc sg'	'stroke, acc sg'

Scholars do not restrict the devoicing from /g/, or argue that Wulfila did not have enough graphs. The process is not marked in /g/ because spirantization and devoicing are not enough to merge it with /h/.⁴⁷ As Moulton writes:

"From this we may deduce that the phonological relationship between postvocalic /g/ and /h/ was not the same as that between /b d z/ and /f þ s/: postvocalic /g/ cannot have been the voiced counterpart of /h/."⁴⁸

⁴⁷ There is dispute over what the additional contrast is between /g/ and /h/. See T. Vennemann, "Phonetic Detail in Assimilation", *Language*, 48 (1972), p. 878.

⁴⁸ W. Moulton, "The Stops and Spirants of Early Germanic", *Language*, 30 (1954) p. 6.

4.2) Middle High German Fortition

Dozens of scribes and poets wrote down their German dialects in the High Middle Ages. In at least our normalized texts, they mark a fortition⁴⁹ in five of six sets of obstruents. Examples of the process syllable finally are taken from Paul.⁵⁰

Lenis

/b/

<lîbe>

'body, dat sg'

<lîp>

'body, nom sg'

/d/

<râde>

'council, dat sg'

<rât>

'council, nom sg'

Fortis

/p/

<tempel>

'temple, nom sg'

No Example

/t/

<râte>

'wheel, dat sg'

<rât>

'wheel, nom sg'

⁴⁹ H. Paul, P. Wiehl and S. Grosse, *Mittelhochdeutsche Grammatik*, 23. Auflage, (Tübingen: Niemayer 1989), §§62.

⁵⁰ Paul (1989).

/g/	/k/
<tage>	erschrecken
'day, dat sg'	'frighten, inf'
<tag>	<erschrac>
'day, nom sg'	'frighten, 3rd sg past'
/v/	/f/
<hove>	<helfen>
'court, dat sg'	'help, inf'
<hof>	<half>
'court, nom sg'	'help, 3rd sg past'
/h/	/χ/
<sehen>	<sprechen>
'see, inf'	'speak, inf'
<sach>	<sprach>
'see, 3rd sg past'	'speak, 3rd sg past'

There is debate on whether the syllable final fricatives had always been fortis, and whether they should be considered reflexes of lenis phonemes.⁵¹ If not, an /h/ in <sehen> and an /χ/ in <sprechen> can differ in more than just fortition,

⁵¹ Braune (1987), §§102.

while an [χ] from /χ/ come in <sach> and <sprach>. In any case, the fortition does not get marked in the lenis dental fricative:

/ž/	/s/
<wîsen>	<wîzen>
'manner, dat pl'	'white, dat pl'
<wîs>	<wîz>
**<wîz>	
'manner, uninfl'	'white, uninfl'

Scholars do not restrict fortition from the dentals, or argue for a shortage of graphs. The process is not marked in /ž/ because fortition was not enough to merge it with /s/.⁵² Moulton writes that /ž/ "differed qualitatively" from /s/, and "hence did not (yet) merge with it in any positions".⁵³

5) Conclusion

Something like the /ž/ of Middle High German and the /h/ of

⁵² There is dispute over what the additional contrast is between /ž/ and /s/. See H. Esau, "The Medieval German Sibilants /s/ and /z/", *Journal of English and Germanic Philology*, 75 (1976), pp. 188-191.

⁵³ Moulton (1954), p. 37. The quote is actually for Old High German, but that is the source of the Middle High German contrast.

Gothic are posited for Notker;⁵⁴ at least syllable initially in the environment of the Anlautgesetz. A fortition would not merge Notker's /ǰ≠s/ or /h≠χ/. But it would merge the remaining four sets of obstruents: /b≠p/, /d≠t/, /g≠k/ and /v≠f/. These are also the only four marked by the Anlautgesetz.

Obstruent processes conditioned by a syllable boundary are marked defectively in Gothic, Middle High German and Notker's Alemannic. The processes do not exempt certain obstruents, and the scribes do not lack graphs. The processes are marked defectively because they do not merge each set of obstruents. The scribes mark these mergers, not the processes themselves.

Collinge concludes his overview of the Anlautgesetz by wondering "whether the practice at Saint Gall was important".⁵⁵ It is just another fortition, and maybe not even one from conversational speech. But the marking of that fortition impacts any language reconstructed from texts. It is fiercely debated whether we can extract anything more than phonemes and their mergers.⁵⁶ Notker's

⁵⁴ Braune (1987), §§154, §§168.

⁵⁵ Collinge (1985), p. 124.

⁵⁶ The issue is addressed implicitly by any phonological analysis based on texts. But for works dealing explicitly with the controversy, see citations in R. King, *Historical Linguistics and Generative Grammar*,

Anlautgesetz can contribute to that debate.

(New Jersey: Englewood Cliffs, 1969), pp. 203-213; J. Voyles, "A History of OHG i-umlaut", *Beiträge zur Geschichte der deutschen Sprache*, 133 (1991), pp. 161-164.